

Evaluation of the genotoxic potential of Lambda-cyhalothrin in cultured lymphocytes of *Rattus norvegicus* (Berkenhout)

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Article Information	Abstract
<p>Article history:</p> <p>Received: 09.09.2012 Revised: 18.10.2012 Accepted: 12.12.2012</p>	<p>The rise of human population has crossed all strides in the beginning of 20th century with the result scientists had to employ all tactics to feed the rising population. During this course some of the synthesized chemicals not only helped the mankind but at the same time became reasons for his agony. λ-cyhalothrin being a third generation pesticide contains α-cyano group and is available in a number of formulations selected for present study to evaluate its effect on genotoxicology. Genotoxic potential of λ-cyhalothrin (LCT) was evaluated <i>in vivo</i> in the cultured albino rat lymphocytes on the basis of chromosomal aberration (CA) assay. The LCT was administered to albino rats as repeated oral doses of 18 mg/kg body weight to acute group; 0.6 mg/kg body weight to sub acute group up to 30 days, while recovery group did not receive any dose after 30 days till day 45. The negative control received the vehicle (ground nut oil) only. Mitomycin C (MMC) was used as a positive control (1.5 mg/kg body weight), administered intraperitoneally. Significant clastogenic potential has been observed after 30 days sub acute treatment. The types of chromosomal aberrations observed in present study include chromosome gap, chromosome break, chromatid gap, chromatid break and fragments. LCT possesses potential to induce cytogenetic changes in lymphocytes, which are mostly used in defense and cell immunity. These changes inform of chromosomal aberrations are indicative of possibility of the experimental compound to exerts stress at such a higher level of food chain. The pyrethroids may be problematic like conventional pesticides of yester years.</p>
<p>Keywords:</p> <p>λ-cyhalothrin (LCT), Chromosomal aberration, albino rat, MMC</p>	

1. INTRODUCTION:

The population of the world is increasing continuously since time immemorial and utilization of natural resources is on increase. The rise of human population has crossed all strides in the beginning of 20th century with the result scientists had to employ all tactics to feed the rising population. It became essential to look for newer avenues to minimize the misery and plight of human population. In this situation few chemicals were synthesized which were identical to natural origins. The pyrethroids were such in this series. To overcome the problem of food requirement, biologically safe pyrethroids are in vogue. However, their indiscriminate use is not free of problems. Unfortunately pesticides have diverse effects on the specific target species. Undesirable side effects are wide spread and include injury to non-target organisms, ecosystem imbalance and environmental contamination by persistent pesticides. Pesticides are biological, physical and

chemical agents used to kill organisms, which are harmful to human beings. Pesticides might be incorporated into plant tissue and food grains and as a result of this they enter into food chain and accumulated at various tropic levels after each generation through biomagnification. Such pesticides are a menace, in a sense that they get entry into the mammalian body and cause alterations in various cytological, biochemical and physiological processes leading to serious complications.

The genotoxic effects of λ -cyhalothrin (LCT) were investigated in various animal species using chromosomal aberration (CA), micronucleus formation (MN) and banding pattern analysis (Agrawal et al., 1994; Campana et al., 1999; Fahmy and Abdalla, 2001; Celik et al., 2003; Sharma, 2004). The bone marrow is most widely used for short-term *in vivo* assay for genotoxic study (Schmidt, 1973; Heddle 1973), however, in the present study lymphocytes have been used as they are functional in defense mechanism and can easily be obtained from

blood of the experimental animal. Although cytotoxic nature of synthetic pyrethroids is a known fact (Pati and Bhunya, 1989; Bhunya and Pati, 1990; Hayashi et al., 1994; Dianovsky and Sivikova, 1995; Nakano et al., 1996; Chauhan et al., 1997; Pandey, 2001; Singh and Saxena, 2002; Sharma, 2004), yet LCT is hereby checked for possessing the cytotoxic potential through chromosomal aberrations analysis. Earlier reports emphasize mainly bone marrow (Celik et al., 2003) for evaluating LCT toxicity however the present studies assess genotoxic potential of LCT in lymphocyte *in vivo*.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

2.1. Test Compound:

For the present study λ -cyhalothrin (LCT), a non-systemic pyrethroid insecticide with the trade name 'Karate' (CAS no. 91465-08-06), chemical name (R+S)-F-cyano-3 methyl-(phenoxyphenyl)-(1S+1R)-cis-3-(2-2chloro-3,3,3-trifluoroprop-1-enyl)-2-2-dimethyl-cyclopropane-carboxylate of 98 % purity, with contact and stomach action and repellent properties was procured from Zeneca-ICI Agro Chemicals, Chennai, India.

2.2. Maintenance of Experimental Albino Rats:

The experimental albino rats (*Rattus norvegicus*, Berkenhout), procured from inbred colony were acclimated for one month to the laboratory conditions (temperature. $25\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$, relative humidity $60\pm 5\%$ and photoperiod 12 hr/day) before using them for the experiment. Adult male

Fig. 1. Percent mortality of λ -cyhalothrin in male and female albino rats, *R. norvegicus* after oral dosing

2.4. Selection of Dose:

2.4.1. Test agent: An oral dose of 18 mg/kg body weight for acute treatment, while for sub acute treatment 1/30 of acute dose was given for 30 days *i.e.* 0.6 mg/kg body weight/day by gavage tube. The recovery group did not receive any dose after 30 days of sub acute treatment till day 45.

and female rats of almost equal size and weight were kept in the polypropylene cages and cleaned regularly to avoid any infection or undesirable odour in the laboratory. Each cage was equipped with a metallic food plate and water bottle. The albino rats were offered fresh feed daily throughout the experimentation on Gold Mohar rat and mice feed, manufactured by Hindustan Lever Ltd., India at regular interval and water was provided *ad libitum*.

2.3. Random Selection of Individuals:

In the present study, for LD₅₀ the data were analyzed statistically by log dose/probit regression line method (Finney, 1971). Oral LD₅₀ of male and female rats was found to be 75.85 mg/kg body weight and 56.695 mg/kg body weight, respectively (Saxena and Sharma, 2002; Sharma, 2004). The percent mortality response in the two sexes as per figure1, did not reveal any significant change ($p>0.05$). Hence, it could be possible to select the individuals randomly (irrespective of sex) for experimentation.

Five healthy adult albino rats (7-8 weeks of age, with average body weight of 150-200 g) were selected randomly for test, control and recovery studies sacrificed after 1, 2, 15, 30 and 45 (recovery) days for the collection of blood. Each rat was assigned a number for convenience prior to experimentation. All the rats of the experimental sets were given doses of LCT orally with the help of gavage tube and those of control sets equal amount of vehicle *i.e.* ground nut oil.

Fig. 2. Frequency of chromosomal aberration (%) in relation to λ -cyhalothrin in albino rat, *R. norvegicus* using cultured lymphocyte

2.4.2. Positive control: Mitomycin C (MMC), CAS no. 50-07-7 was used as a positive control. MMC was given as a single dose of 1.5 mg/kg bwt via intraperitoneal injection. It is acceptable that a positive control is administered by a route different from or the same as the test agent and that it is given only a single time (Hayashi et al., 1994).

2.4.3. Negative control: Negative controls consisting of vehicle (groundnut oil) were treated with all treatment groups.

2.5. Collection of Blood Samples:

In the early morning hours (7-8 am) on the due date of autopsy the rats were warmed under the desk lamp to facilitate bleeding. Enough care was taken to avoid them going into heat shock. Over heated condition was depicted by beads of perspiration on the nose or excessive activity. The rats were placed in a restraining block and swabbed the tail first with 70% ethanol, then with 90% ethanol. After the alcohol was evaporated, a small slit was made in the underside of the tail about 1 inch from the base of the tail by a flamed razor blade. First two drops of blood were discarded to avoid contamination; Blood collecting tubes were gently flamed just before and just after the blood was collected. After collection 8-10 drops of blood, the tube was agitated gently to mix the blood and heparin solution. The blood collecting tubes were tightly capped and stored at 37°C.

2.6. Chromosomal Aberration Assay:

Chromosomal aberration was performed in cultured lymphocyte according to the methodology proposed by Triman et al. (1975) with slight modifications.

2.6.1. Inoculation of culture: For culture 0.1 ml of the blood-heparin mixture was added to each prepared culture vials containing 0.1 ml phytohemagglutinin (PHA) and 0.8 ml supplemented medium (containing RPMI 1640, 25 mM Hepes buffer, fetal calf serum and penicillin-streptomycin solution), to bring the final culture volume to 1.0 ml. The cultures were mixed well and capped tightly. The cultures were incubated at an angle of approximately 5° from horizontal at 37°C for 24 hours.

2.6.2. Culture growth in media: The cultures were centrifuged after 24 hours at 200 x g for 8 min. The supernatant was removed and discarded aseptically with a sterile Pasteur pipette. The medium was replaced with 0.8 ml of supplemented medium and 0.1 ml of PHA. The culture was mixed gently; bubbling was avoided, with a sterile Pasteur pipette, and returned to the 37°C incubator for another 24 hours. 5 µg of colchicine was added to each culture at 48 hours and mixed gently and thoroughly with a Pasteur pipette. It was incubated at 37°C for an additional 4 hours.

2.6.3. Harvesting and hypotonic treatment of cells: Each culture was transferred to a 15 ml conical centrifuge tube and centrifuged at 200 x g for 8 min at 52 hours. The supernatant was removed carefully

with a Pasteur pipette. 1.0 ml of 0.075 M KCl was added slowly to the cells without disturbing the pellet. The culture was mixed gently with a Pasteur pipette and bubbling was avoided. The cultures were returned to the 37°C incubator for 10 min, centrifuged them at 1200 rpm for 10 min.

2.6.4. Fixation: The supernatant was carefully removed with a Pasteur pipette leaving a volume approximately 0.25 ml including the cell pellet. Chilled fixative (glacial acetic acid: methonal, 1:3) was added very slowly down the inside of tube to avoid clumping of the lysed cells. When the total volume of the culture and fixative become 1.0 ml, mixed it gently by rapid pipetting. 1.0 ml of fixative was then added to bring the volume to 2.0 ml and mixed the culture again. At this point the culture was tightly capped and refrigerated overnight.

2.6.5. Slide preparation and staining: Before slide preparation culture was centrifuged at 1200 rpm for 5 minutes, removed the supernatants fixative (leaving the volume of 0.5 ml), and added 1.5 ml of fresh fixative. This washing procedure was repeated two more times before using this for slide preparation. Two drops of above suspension were dropped on to a clean, chilled, wet slide. The sides and back of slide were quickly blotted and simultaneously blew once across slide and placed onto slide warmer to dry. Slides were immediately coded with a random number, which had been correlated with the animal number. The dried slides were stained in 4% Giemsa (in phosphate buffer pH 6.8). Slides were dried thoroughly, and cover slips were applied.

2.6.6. Metaphase scoring: Hundred well spread intact metaphases were scored through blind scoring from each animal number under 100 x oil immersion. The abnormalities suggested by the "Ad Hoc Committee of Environmental Mutagen Society and The Institute for Medical Research" (1972) were considered which included chromatid and chromosome breaks, fragments of untraceable origin. Chromatid and chromosome gaps were recorded but were not included as aberrant features in the final evaluation (Myles et al., 1978). The values were calculated by using following formula (Singh and Saxena, 2002).

2.6.7. Frequency of aberrant cells:

$$\text{Frequency of aberrant cells} = \frac{\text{Total aberrant cells}}{\text{Total No. of cells studied}}$$

2.6.8. Percentage of aberrations:

$$\text{Percentage of aberrations} = \frac{\text{Total aberration (excluding gaps)}}{\text{Total No. of cells studied}} \times 100$$

2.7 Statistical Analysis:

The data collected are compared by 't' test and expressed as mean±SE.

3. RESULTS:

The metaphase analysis of the lymphocytes revealed various types of chromosomal aberrations, which consisted of chromatid, chromosome gaps and breaks, and fragments. Relatively higher frequencies of gaps and fragments were observed for all the doses tested (Table 1). A quantitative assessment of the distribution of breaks and gaps revealed that the

distal regions of the long chromosomes were more vulnerable to the effects of LCT. The frequency of CA is increased with increasing concentrations of LCT (Fig. 2), and statistically non-significant ($P > 0.05$). Differences from the negative control were observed, except at the 30 days sub acute treatment ($P < 0.05$). The mean of the induced CA were range from 0.8 ± 0.55 to 3.6 ± 0.55 in different treatment groups, while in recovery groups it was 1.6 ± 0.84 on comparison to controls. Such values were much lower than those induced by the positive control Mitomycin C (1.5 mg/kg bwt) (15.2 ± 1.2).

Table 1. Chromosomal aberration analysis in peripheral blood lymphocytes of albino rat, *R. norvegicus*

S. No.	Treatment	Dose (mg/kg b. w.)	No. of individuals treated	Treatment time (in days)	No. of Cells / animal	Chromosomal aberration				Total		% of aberration without gap		Frequency of aberrant cell		
						Chromatid Chromosome	Chromatid Chromosome	Fragments	Without Gap	With Gap	Mean± S.E.	Significance	Mean± S.E.	Significance		
1.	Negative Control		5	01	250/5	1	-	1	-	1	2	3	0.8 ± 0.55		0.004 ± 0.004	
2.	Acute	18	5	01	250/5	2	-	1	-	1	2	4	0.8 ± 0.55	$p > 0.05$	0.016 ± 0.008	$p > 0.05$
3.	Negative Control		5	02	250/5	1	-	1	-	1	2	3	0.8 ± 0.55		0.004 ± 0.004	
4.	Acute	18	5	02	250/5	1	-	1	-	2	3	4	1.2 ± 0.55	$p > 0.05$	0.004 ± 0.004	$p > 0.05$
5.	Negative Control		5	15	250/5	1	1	-	1	1	2	4	0.8 ± 0.55		0.008 ± 0.005	
6.	Sub-acute	0.6	5	15	250/5	2	1	1	1	1	3	6	1.2 ± 0.55	$p > 0.05$	0.012 ± 0.009	$p > 0.05$
7.	Negative Control		5	30	250/5	1	-	1	-	1	2	3	0.8 ± 0.55		0.008 ± 0.005	
8.	Sub-acute	0.6	5	30	250/5	1	1	2	3	4	9	11	3.5 ± 0.55	$p < 0.05$	0.036 ± 0.008	$p < 0.02$
9.	Negative Control		5	45	250/5	2	-	-	1	1	2	4	0.8 ± 0.55		0.008 ± 0.005	
10.	Recovery	0.0	5	45	250/5	1	1	1	1	2	4	5	1.6 ± 0.84	$p > 0.05$	0.008 ± 0.005	$p > 0.05$
11.	Positive Control	1.5	5	2	250/5	13	11	15	12	11	38	62	15.2 ± 1.2	$p < 0.001$	0.120 ± 0.050	$p < 0.01$

4. DISCUSSION:

In the present investigation, non-significant induction of clastogenic activity of 3-cyhalothrin has been observed in acute, sub acute (15ds) treatment, and recovery groups, while in 30ds sub acute treatment clastogenic potential has been observed. Similarly workers of USEPA (1989) and WHO (1990) working group failed to observe clastogenic potential under LCT stress, while Campana et al. (1999), Fahmy and Abdalla (2001) and Celik et al. (2003) demonstrated clastogenic potential of λ-cyhalothrin in fish, mouse and wistar rat in red blood cells and bone marrow, respectively. The findings in the present studies are in accordance to previous reports on the clastogenic potential of synthetic pyrethroids as manifested in rodent bone marrow (Amer et al.,

1993; Hrelia et al., 1994; Dianovsky and Sivikova, 1995; Nakano et al., 1996; Oraby, 1997; Singh and Saxena, 2002; Celik et al., 2003) in human peripheral lymphocyte cultures (Surralles et al., 1990; Dolara et al., 1992; Barrueco et al., 1994; Dianovsky and Sivikova, 1995), in CHO cells (Caballo et al., 1992; Barrueco et al., 1992) and in aquatic organisms (Campana et al., 1999; Caves and Ergene-Gozukara, 2003).

The effect of LCT seems to be time of exposure and concentration dependent. In 30ds sub acute treatment a significant difference in aberration has been observed, might be due to the longer duration of treatment. Hence, LCT has greater potential for inducing chromosomal aberration in long duration treatments, while its effect has been found to be non-significant in short term treatment

(Bhunya, and Pati, 1990; Ghosh et al., 1992; Carfagna et al., 1996; Celik et al., 2003). In addition, chemicals that cause damage to lysosomes and membranes of cellular system, induce the release of lysosomal or other DNAase into the cytoplasm of damaged cell and induce DNA double strand break and in those cells that survive sub lethal damage, such double strand breaks could have a variety of genotoxic effects such as mutation, chromosome aberration (Sharma, 2004).

The clastogenic property of LCT may be due to its ability to cause degenerative and necrotic damage to mammalian tissue like other pesticides (Rahman et al., 2000; Kokuritsu et al., 2003), which may probably induce lysosomal damage and release of hydrolytic enzymes. Release of hydrolytic enzymes as a result of lysosomal damage following cybil intoxication has been observed (Singh and Saxena, 2001; Saxena and Doneriya, 2004). Further, cypermethrin has been seen causing major degenerative changes in rat bone marrow cells (Pandey, 2001; Singh & Saxena, 2002).

The frequency of chromosomal aberrations was directly related to the concentration used and duration after exposure to fenvalerate in Swiss albino mice (Carfagna et al., 1996), while cytolethality was time; concentration and cell number dependent in rats is already a known fact. Further, Chauhan et al., (1997) observed greater potential of cypermethrin and deltamethrin as genotoxic agent in mice. It is thus evident that different kinds of mechanism are responsible for toxicity and clastogenicity on one side and DNA breakage and gene mutation on the other side (Sharma, 2004).

The non-significant increase in recovery group is also supported by Amer and Aboul-Ela (1985), who found that frequency of chromosomal aberration returning to normal levels of control after 14ds recovery following cypermethrin toxicity in mice, while Amer et al. (1993) revealed percentage of chromosomal aberration to be decreased as time lapses after treatment. Similarly, Sharma et al. (1988) observed that elevation in the frequency was steep up to 10th day, but it was slowed down with an increase in dose and time after 2, 4-DB acid toxicity in mice. Similar mechanism may also be responsible for non-significant increase of chromosomal aberration in recovery group.

The selected cyno group derivative (λ -cyhalothrin, type-II pyrethroid) has a potential to induce genotoxic alterations in peripheral blood leucocytes particularly lymphocytes which forces its regulated application in the ecosystem else the chemical may prove its worth as a future mutagen like the conventional IInd and IIIrd generation pesticides of yester years.

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